

The Impact of Covid-19 on the Promotion of Employment at Nonthaburi Province

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Abstract:- The economy of Nonthaburi Province in 2020 and the trend in 2021 found that in terms of economic growth, the Nonthaburi Provincial Treasury Office has estimated the economy of Nonthaburi Province in 2020 will shrink -9.2 (with a forecast range of -10.1 to -8.2%) This was supported by the contraction of the service sector in the industrial sector. "New Normal" lifestyle after the COVID-19 crisis, is the first and most noticeable thing. It is expected that everyone must be directly involved. Lifestyles must change into something called the "New Normal" or "New Normal", so The researcher is therefore interested in studying the impact of Covid-19 on promoting employment in Nonthaburi Province. The objective was to study the impact of Covid-19 on promoting employment. Nonthaburi Province by collecting data from a population group of 445 people in Nonthaburi Province and using a questionnaire as a tool. Statistics used in data analysis were percentage (percentage) in measuring the personal characteristics of the respondents, mean (mean), and standard deviation. (SD.) Descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation were used. The results of the research showed that the results of the test for employment promotion relations in the COVID-19 era in various aspects (Y1) found that in the domestic employment (X1) aspect, the P-value was 0.001, which was less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$) and foreign workers (X2) has a P-value equal to 0.001, less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), that is, reject the main hypothesis H_0 accepts the secondary hypothesis H_1 means that opinions about promoting employment in the COVID-19 era At least one aspect influence opinions about promoting employment in the COVID-19 era. Population Nonthaburi province, which can be written in the form of the regression analysis as follows: $Y = 103.789 + 1.455 (X_1) + 3.035 (X_2)$.

Keywords:- The Impact of Covid-19, The Promotion of Employment, Nonthaburi Province.

I. INTRODUCTION

Thailand's unemployment rate hits highest in 5 years Quarter 1 of 2021, the quarterly unemployment rate in Thailand [1] is the highest compared to the past 5 years and the highest since the start of the COVID-19 crisis to 1.96%, which has increased from the past before the epidemic. and last year The percentage of people in Thailand who do not have jobs is called the unemployment rate. is on average 1%. The 4th wave of the COVID-19 epidemic affected online job posting [2] by 48%, reflecting the company's slowdown in hiring, and the direction of online job posting in Thailand. From birth COVID-19 Outbreak The first wave during March 2020 to the current 4th wave, compared to January 2020, found that the first wave of COVID-19 spread during March. And the state announced Lockdown, resulting in online job postings across the country at a negative 36%, but after Thailand was able to control the number of infected people and the state unlocked Lockdown, posting jobs through online channels Recovering to grow, The second time COVID-19 is spreading widely. epidemic born in December The number of infected people is not large. But as a result, online job postings dropped more than the first wave. [3] which during this outbreak 46% negative online job posting Three waves of the COVID-19 epidemic The trend of online job posting has improved, with a negative 13% compared to January 2020 Because entrepreneurs have been through 2 waves of crises, [4] they have begun to understand the cycle of the situation. And for a while, it will get better, the 4th WAVE OF the COVID-19 epidemic with the worsening epidemic situation. And there are more infected people every day. As a result, business operators expected that the situation from the 3rd wave that continued into the 4th wave would improve, did not turn out as expected. As a result, online job postings dropped by 48%.

Fig.1. Unemployment rate and GDP of Thailand (Jobdb.com)

Employment is expected to decrease until the end of 2021 – "Vaccine against COVID-19"[5] is an important variable in the job market. What is interesting to watch is the situation of the 4th wave of the COVID-19 epidemic that has spread heavily. And the number of infected people is still high. had a serious impact on employment. It is expected that employment may decrease until the end of 2021 when December is the Low Season. of the job market (the high season of the job market is January and May). Vaccination distribution is a key factor in building confidence. May create a change in employment to revive. The economy of Nonthaburi Province in 2020 and the trend in 2021 found that in terms of economic growth, the Nonthaburi Provincial Treasury Office has estimated the economy of Nonthaburi Province in 2020 will shrink -9.2(with a forecast range of -10.1 to -8.2%)This was supported by the contraction of the service sector in the industrial sector. " New Normal" lifestyle after the COVID-19 crisis, is the first and most noticeable thing. It is expected that everyone must be directly involved. Lifestyles that must change into something called "New Normal" or "New Normal",

➤ *Research Objectives*

The objective was to study the impact of Covid-19 on promoting employment. Nonthaburi Province in Thailand.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researcher is interested in Coronavirus is affecting many aspects of life. promotion of employment in Nonthaburi Province by collecting data from a population group of 445 people in Nonthaburi Province and using a questionnaire as a tool. Statistics used in data analysis were percentage (percentage) in measuring the personal characteristics of the respondents, mean (mean), and standard deviation. (SD.) Descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation were used.

III. RESULTS

The results of the research showed that the level of opinions about promoting employment in the era of COVID-19 The overall picture is at a high level. when considering

side by side The aspect with the highest level of opinion was the aspect of domestic employment. Followed by Thai workers abroad and the least is foreign workers It can be concluded that the variable selected into the equation is domestic employment. foreign workers The multiple correlation coefficient (Multiple R) was 0.842, the coefficient of determination (R Square) was 0.709, the adjusted coefficient of work (Adjusted R Square) was 0.674, and the standard error in the system (Standard Error) was 26.830.The research showed that the results of the test for employment promotion relations in the COVID-19 era in various aspects (Y₁) found that in the domestic employment (X₁) aspect, the P-value was 0.001, which was less than 0.05 (0.000 < 0.05) and foreign workers(X₂) has a P-value equal to 0.001, less than 0.05(0.000 < 0.05), that is, reject the main hypothesis Ho accepts the secondary hypothesis H₁ means that opinions about promoting employment in the COVID-19 era At least one aspect influence opinions about promoting employment in the COVID-19 era. Population Nonthaburi province, which can be written in the form of the regression analysis as follows: $Y=103.789 + 1.455 (X_1) + 3.035 (X_2)$

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The results were discovered in this study.

- Entrepreneurship Technology preparation company to support work in the fully digital age and Aware of social-environmental policies and culture of equality Embracing Gender Diversity and Emphasizing Upskill/Reskill.
- Workers are open to acquiring new skills. to create stability and advance in your career create an attitude of endless learning Especially IT and digital knowledge, in addition to hard skills, soft skills must be given priority such as Growth Mindset, Leadership.
- Employment promotion in the COVID-19 era in various aspects (Y₁), it was found that domestic employment (X₂) had a P-value of 0.001, less than 0.05 (0.000 < 0.05), and for migrant workers. (X₂) has a P-value equal to 0.001, is less than 0.05(0.000 < 0.05), that is, reject the main hypothesis Ho, accept the secondary hypothesis H₁. This means that opinions promoting employment in the age of COVID-19 At least one aspect influence opinions about promoting employment in the COVID-19 era. Population Nonthaburi province, which can be written in the form of the regression analysis as follows: $Y=103.789 + 1.455 (X_1) + 3.035 (X_1)$

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The Entrepreneurship Technology preparation company to support work in the fully digital age and Aware of social-environmental policies and culture of equality Embracing Gender Diversity and Emphasizing Upskill/Reskill. Workers are open to acquiring new skills. to create stability and advance in your career create an attitude of endless learning Especially IT and digital knowledge, in addition to hard skills, soft skills must be given priority such as Growth Mindset, Leadership.

จำนวนประกาศงานออนไลน์ในประเทศไทย (รวม Marketplace และ Aggregator)

FIG.2. POPULATION OF ONLINE JOBS IN THAILAND (JOBS DB.COM)

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